

THE CONCEPT OF „*MELO-PSYCHO-NUTRITION*” (MPN), IN PSYCHO-GASTRONOMY STUDIES

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Abstract. *The paper centers on the achievement of a unitary psycho-gastronomy concept on direction of the phonic impact upon nutrition. There are aggregated a series of fragmentary observations of gastrophysics linked to the psychologic impact of musical sounds in relation to the feeding manner, to gastronomy. The paper methodologically approaches vibrational frequencies in the relation between harmonious sounds and living organism. There are defined the phrase „organismic meloimpact” (for all positive, neuter or negative situations, at all species) and „melotherapy” (when the effect is positive, especially in relation to the human species). There is defined the concept and highlighted the melo-psycho-nutrition method necessary to the harmonization of all the elements of the process of organismic meloimpact, with consequences in equilibrating the metabolic balance regarding nutrition and food assimilation. There is taken into consideration productivity growth at planetary level, or in animal production, as well as the improvement of the dynamic balance regarding food digestibility at the human species, as final element in the trophic chain. As for man and human society in general, there are mainly analyzed aspects linked to the finality of the alimentary act by culinary production, in relation to the problem of psycho-gastronomy. There are exemplified certain practical applications at the level of the restauration system and, in general, in the hospitality industry.*

Keywords: gastro physics, food, Melos, nutrition, psychology

1. Introduction

We specify that gastrophysics has recently entered among sciences, and its demarche to reveal how our senses combine between themselves and even reciprocally condition, in order to influence perception upon what we eat. There is practically analyzed the combination between gastronomy and psychophysics in order to search the multitude of ingredients (apparently peripheral ones) that influence our organoleptic perceptions (of flavor, of taste etc.). Thus our culinary choices may be directed so that we may make the difference between a „*memorable meal*” and one that may be forgotten.

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Gastrophysics is in essence the new science about food consumption beyond what ordinary food means [8], demarche that presents itself as a full of interesting promises research field, practically many sciences and study fields benefitting from its fruit (dietetics, neurology, psychology, sociology, public health, marketing, design and others).

In other words, in order to take maximum advantage of every menu, we will have to „*think not only about what is in our mouth, but also about what is in our mind*”.

We practically direct towards gastronomic psychology, biomedically based on psycho-nutrition (*nutritional psychology*), i.e. the link between emotions and the way we eat. We are speaking about the psychology of food consumption, respectively nutritional psychology, which is the science of the manner nutrients affect the state of mind and behavior [14, 15]. This field examines the relation between food and our inner experience, enlightening the physiological and biological mechanisms, influenced by the nutrient contribution that stay at the bases of our mood and behavior [4, 5, 6, 9, 11, and others].

In fact, our senses interact in order to offer us the complex feeling we have whenever we eat or drink something. Eating is a multi-sensorial experience, implying much more senses and much more impressions than it was thought [12, 13]. That is to say not only the taste, the sense of smell and the aspect of a meal, but also different exterior factors (as for example musical sounds) with no connection with food indirectly „affect” the respective food, making it seem better or less good.

All that has been said is based on numerous examples, so that the starting point in the scientific demarche of **gastrophysics** is represented by observations and questions from the reality of the gastronomic field. Without entering into details, we enumerate some ascertainments and questions: white wine seems better in a room lit in red or blue; it seems that we are quicker fed up and feel we have eaten more if we eat from small dishes, than if we eat the same helpings from large dishes; that the weight of the utensils we are eating certain complex food with influences us, as well as the position of the food on the dish, even without knowing anything about the respective food. We can also enumerate a series of questions: Why on planes it is drunk more tomato juice (27% from the bought drinks)? What is the effect of serving food on small plates, or red ones, or circular ones? Why we eat 35% more food whenever we eat with another person and 75% more when there are three persons at table? What is the influence of food smell upon the human brain? We speak here about aspects linked to „*human brain flavor system*”, developing a new scientific field: **neurogastronomy** [7]. Then,

what is the influence of background music? This last question being the subject of the present study too.

In this context, we may analyze the **ambiance** of the place we are eating in, taking into consideration the psychological impact [3]. Therefore, a food taste does not mean everything. We participate at the eating act with much more senses than we used to think and there is a large number of elements that influence what we think and feel about that food. There become important: the music we are listening to, the light around us, the color of the dishes, the utensils size, even the name given to the food we are eating – everything influences our and may subtly make the difference between an „acceptable” meal and a great one [1,10].

Psycho-gastronomy has ancient roots. One of these, linked to *sound perception*, shows that, starting with ancient customs, as for example spells (white magic) practiced in old times, they are whispered, emphasizing certain key words by incantations, that give off a certain frequency that resonate with the human organism. Not to mention the text messages, when music is also accompanied by words. Nowadays incantation has lost part of its force to penetrate the human psyche, but there become relative a balancing relation by „restaurant music” in relation to the eaten food (what type of music assures a better pleasure, creates harmony or, more directly said, a better psychic state and a better digestion? Or it has a negative impact?).

Taking into consideration what has been exposed, the paper has as an **objective** the study of sound perception and their psychological impact in relation to the feeding manner, to gastronomy.

2. Material and methods

The research methodology is based on VIBRATIONAL FREQUENCIES, on other physic principles and, especially, on the quantic mechanics demarche. The sound study and their parametrization have as an analyses element the indicator: *Hertz (Hz)*. It is known that this parameter indicates the number of cycles per second of the respective band and man has the capacity to perceive frequencies between 15 Hz and 20,000 Hz. There are approached study methods of sensorial analyses, neurogastronomy principles and gastrophysics concepts.

3. Results and discussions

Recent studies try to rehabilitate from scientific perspective the **music influence** upon organism, obviously complementarily with the psychological impact. Therefore, we are mentioning that sonorous wave action is known both upon plants which germinate and grow better, and milk productivity, at cows when music is sung or listened to in their stables. Thus there are rediscovered multiple virtues of music: it doesn't have only a part, a cultural esthetic function, as certain

people may think at first sight, but also a magic, PHYLOSOPHICAL FUNCTION, of *organismic impact* and even a *therapeutic* side. From here also the phrases „*organismic meloimpact*” (for all positive, neuter or negative situations at all species) and „*melotherapy*” (when the effect becomes positive upon metabolism, especially in relation to the human species).

A new light is given by **quantic mechanics** that generally admits that **matter is nothing but vibration**. Decomposition in the smallest components practically leads to the existence of *particles and bands*. Atoms (nucleus and electrons that rotate around it) confer each substance, by number, the electrons and their orbits, a specific set of **vibrational frequencies**. From here one may deduce that nothing is solid mass, just nucleuses surrounded by bands that endlessly rotate. „All is in movement and vibration” (from time to time) with an incredible speed [2].

There may be considered that every being at individual level (organism) vibrates at a certain low frequency, in fact similarly to all things that are in vibration and vibrate at their own frequency. *Food* is not an exception, it has of course its own frequency, and here being a generous space for research.

The fact that everything is in vibration implicitly means that all that exists creates and gives off sounds. Extrapolating, we can say that particular frequency of all food and organisms may be interpreted as being a sound and, from here, their parametrization by indicator *Hertz (Hz)*. The human being intrinsically has a frequency universe that superpose and the result is a “symphony” having cosmic proportions, being thus able to resonate with the rest of the world, therefore including, and maybe more directly, FOOD.

The process practically indicates that sounds having the same frequency enter in resonance, i.e. there is produced a low frequency sonorous band (which is called *resonance*), from where we may deduce that THE ORGANISM AND FOOD ARE IN RESONANCE, meaning that vibrations that characterize them attract one another and interact between them. More than that, vibrational frequencies inevitably lead to balance or lack of balance. When frequencies are fundamentally incompatible, they can't enter in resonance. But after the theories of the Japanese *Masaru Emoto* (2006), resonance may also exist when frequencies are not identical, and most of the things in nature give off stable frequencies. **Harmony** becomes thus possible and, why not, in our opinion, *the harmony organism-food by organismic meloimpact or, as the case may be, by melotherapy*.

If we introduce into the equation all the described elements, we may launch the hypothesis that leads to the idea of superposing principles, so that we may treat music **in relation to nutrition, by the “melo-psycho-nutrition” concept**.

Music and its virtues, with benefic, healing effects, may reach the level of *therapy through music*. Therefore, **melotherapy** is the method cure or to attenuate

symptoms by listening to music. On the other hand, from a technical-biological perspective, we may sustain that *the organismic impact by music* has stimulative effects upon the organismic physique (at all kingdoms) and, of course, upon psyche too, in case of men. From this perspective, in our opinion, **joining the musical sound to the food act** in relation to the body impact and the human psyche, we may define the "*melo-psycho-nutrition*" phrase.

MELO-PSYCHO-NUTRITION (MPN) is the concept based on the analyses of the sound impact upon different persons, in the idea to stimulate men's organism by „Melos” both from the “psycho-metabolic” perspective in relation to digestion, and „psycho-hedonic” one in relation to the welfare offered by food, with the enjoyment or with the pleasure to eat, as well as the extension in the *infrahuman world* to stimulate productive performances of animals or plants, through music in relation to the feeding act and different reflexes.

The direct observation linked to men's food manner habits show that no wonder it has gained ground that in public houses having a meal is accompanied with music (as a rule, accompaniment music or pop, jazz or musical shows). This tandem „music-food”, beyond the usual pleasure, may be approached by the MPN concept which introduces a series of **experimental perspectives and work hypothesis**. Thus, we will start all from observations and questions: What music has the virtue to stimulate or heal (melotherapy)? What music has a negative impact (disruption of digestion etc.)? What rhythm does it have and in what relation is it with organism biorhythm? In what ambience is it listened to (in a restaurant, in a bar, in special halls etc.)? What are the listening conditions? Which should be the appropriate sound level (as a measure in acoustics in *decibels / dB*) and others. Therefore we open a study “slope”, where many experiments are still necessary.

Without entering into details, we consider as a research way in MPN the idea that music has the capacity to **induce info-energetic balance** through the *bioresonance* phenomenon induced by sound vibrations, probably especially by instrumental music. This one because the “wordless” meaning of music is the one to confer it power and value, as one communicates through music: all human feeling scale, natural phenomena, suggestion of seasons, of day and night moments with their ineffable fascination, wonderful landscapes, force, energy mobilization or, on the contrary, their dissipation, their waste in the galactic ocean.

Thus we may “prosaically” experiment both the effect of the „melodic field” (Melos) upon organism, and, as for nutrition, *food vibrations* upon organism, as well as harmony (or disharmony) commonly created upon organism, of *musical*

ambiance during meal. We are referring to a **compatibility and complementarity of music vibrations with the vibrations of the alimentary act (of food and of digestion) based on the melo-psycho-nutrition concept**. Applying the MPN methodology we launch the hypothesis that **food encoded acts (probably through bioresonance mechanism)** and one may consider them as a “melody”. The concatenation of vibration frequencies characteristic for the analyzed organs is unique and it must resonate with the specific “melody” offered by the environment (i.e.: food together with musical ambiance), releasing necessary energy to decode vibrations for nutrition high efficiency (or to start the remedy, in case of organs with certain injuries).

Another element of the MPN concept refers to **the biological rhythm and the musical one**. It is the essential element that confers the comfort or discomfort estate and that connects the audience (listener) to the time feeling. It is known that, during intrauterine life, the fetus listens to his mother’s heart beating. It is to this rhythm that he gets used in a context of maximum protection at body’s temperature. The drums’ rhythm at primitive peoples is exactly this rhythm, and in medieval and classic music we find the well-known rhythm from our life beyond memory, deposited beyond the back of our mind.

The melody and rhythm problem seem to be better known in the **restauration system**. Thus, in public houses it is recommended as a rule to listen at least three musical pieces, their choice being made in function of the type of consumer. We are referring to the educational level, musical culture, affective estate, kind of event one participates at, the moment along the menu and, if the case is, to the diagnostic (in therapy, when man is sick). As an observation, it is recommended that, during the audition, the environment temperature be of 20-22⁰C (with limits between 18-24 degrees).

The **melo-psycho-nutrition** concept (as well as melotherapy and other methods of the organismic meloimpact), has immediate practical applications. Its principles and methods may thus be used, both in prophylactic aim and in curative aim. From this perspective, in the future, when studies have confirmed, the gastronomic specialist is the one to be able to select musical fragments in function of the menu and consumer (!).

Therefore, to create „ambiance” in a restaurant is in fact an application of psychogastronomy too. Thus, choosing a melody, arranging the tables, the form of the dishes, the color of the table napkins etc., are only a few examples in that direction. There are studies [16] that show how color (including the color of the napkins) psychologically influence the dish taste. Probably problems still need to thoroughgoing study, but the beginning shows that pink napkins increase sweet

taste perception, blue napkins increase eggs and Indian spicy food flavor, and orange or yellow napkins will reduce salinity sensation.

Therefore we speak about (multiple) integration elements through which alimentation is studied and defined from balance and harmony perspective. We are referring thus to *integronic dynamics* of the alimentation processes [3], taking into account its nutritive, metabolic, genetic, ecologic and psychologic components, specific for the alimentary act. The **Melo-Psycho-Nutrition** (MPN) concept is therefore a specific and implicit component of *modern cuisine especially based on health-generating principles* that contribute to harmonize the food manner in relation to mind and emotional balance, i.e. a distinct side in *integronic alimentation: environment - food - organism*.

Conclusions

- (1). The study of sound perception and their psychological impact in relation to the feeding manner, to gastronomy, shows that every organism vibrates at a certain low frequency, but also at its own frequency, which may induce the compatibility and complementarity of music vibrations with the alimentary act vibrations (of food and digestion) based on the principles of melo-psycho-nutrition (MPN) concept.
- (2). Melo-psycho-nutrition is a method of *organismic meloimpact* to stimulate the human organism through sound, both from „psycho-metabolic” perspective in relation to digestion, and „psycho-hedonic” in relation to the welfare estate offered by food, to enjoyment or pleasure to eat, and in the infrahuman world, of stimulation of animal or plant productive performances through music in relation to the feeding act.
- (3). The application of the melo-psycho-nutrition concept may be found in the complementarity between musical circuits and the touring program themes (i.e. well professionally programmed restaurant music, musical fragments being selected in function of the menu and consumer), that may lead to satisfaction, or even to exceptional feelings, which makes the melo-psycho-nutrition process be an implicit component of the health generating cuisine, thus contributing to the harmonization of the food manner in relation to mental and emotional balance.
- (4). Empiric observations linked to a better nutrition and digestion in relation to a certain melody induce the hypotheses that especially classic music harmony will have a beneficial effect (experimented in animal breeding to stimulate milk production), which concerning the human species imposes further thorough researches, especially on direction of parametrization and quantification at physical and mental level.

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CONVERGENCE OF ACADEMIC ACTIVITY BETWEEN ROMANIA AND THE EUROPEAN UNION

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Abstract. *One of the numerous problems that need to pass through convergence processes in order to continuously increase the dynamics of European integration is also academic activity, respectively the science field, the research and development one and the didactic activity of university education. The aim of the paper is to analyze elements of convergence between the academic activity from Romania and the one from the European Union. As general objective, through comparisons and statistics, we propose to monitor common elements and existing disharmonies and by the found solutions to contribute to streamline the Romanian academic activity. As a punctual objective, the study wishes that, by a manner of „auditing” type, to propose an indicative model, a reconceptualization of the Romanian university field, necessary to certain corrections to be made. Also another punctual objective proposes to highlight certain necessary aspects (networks) to compatibilize in a greater extent the approached themes, in relation to the similar one from the European Union, in order to achieve a real and beneficial convergence between the union states and, first of all, of our country and EU..*

Keywords: academic activity, convergence, efficiency, research, university education

1. Introduction

No matter the moment syncope, the process of European integration, of „continentalization” will continue, being an objective process of the progression of the present world, so technologized and with forms of internationalization and globalization in all fields. From this perspective, in order to understand things, education becomes priority, field in which the lack of compatibility and homogeneity is of the hour. It is, of course, a difficult process, many of times controversial, but more and more useful to academic collaborations all over the world. In this context, we consider useful an analyses linked to European academic compatibility, in general, and to the convergence of academic activity Romania – the European Union in special.

As a first objective, we propose to start from a *diagnoses* of principle of the Romanian academic complexity, with the identification of the main elements of dysfunctionality and a systemic reconceptualization.

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Another objective is to highlight certain directions and a series of concrete solutions that may effectively lead to the convergence of the academic activity from Romania with the one in EU. The aim of the proposed objectives is to streamline this crucial field for our country.

Academic activity, defined by numerous bibliographic papers [10,11,12], represents the ensemble of physical, intellectual and moral acts made in order to get a certain result concerning the development of one country's science and culture, respectively of institutions and superior schools. Physical, intellectual and moral acts are to be found at academic level, in the basic mission of academic structures, namely: the research mission, the didactic one, as well as the one to disseminate scientific and cultural knowledge.

An institutional innovation specific to the **knowledge emergent society**, that gives a new relevance to superior education and scientific research, is to constitute a new type of organization: *the cooperation heterogeneous network*. They are based on the idea of **harmonization** by institutionalized cooperation between types of activities, institutions, different social actors that until now used to activate separately, not in competition.

Networks are NOT characterized as a formal type of organization, but as a „*moral relation based on trust, on social capital*” [3,6]. A convergence element of these types of networks is *to share resources* so that participants may have access to others' resources.

Among the numerous structures of this type we may mention *The research and technical innovation networks* (initiated even since the year 1998), and more recently there is initiated to link excellence in research centers from Europe to the network and to join scientific communities, firms and scientists from western Europe and from eastern Europe (after CEC / 2000) [9].

For **Romania**, the evolutions that take place at international level represent a chance, the one of the integration into the transition process from the industrial society to the knowledge society, through convergence and without covering precursory stages. Practically, the main resources of the knowledge society are NOT any more material resources and money, but **knowledge**, preponderantly illustrated by human and social capital. Power is not any more given by money (that assure resource control and distribution), but it is given by knowledge, that assures resource balanced distribution and the mobility of the job factor [8].

2. Material and methods

In the study there are used methods such as: diagnoses, prognoses, monitoring, and comparison. Also there are used a series of specific properties of the management of academic activity (conceptual analyses on principles of European

integration; managerial analyses of supervision and guidance of the Romanian academic activity; utilization of comparisons and statistics regarding academic activity).

3. Results and discussions

Starting from the idea that, as a consequence of the development tendency, „KNOWLEDGE” becomes the main „pawn” of this evolution, and to pursue the process of *continental convergence* of the education by knowledge is more than opportune, we consider that this one may lead to **complementary unification of principles** of education approach, of formation and information in the EU space.

In the carried out analyses we will approach the idea of convergence of the Romanian academic life with the one in EU, pursuing four directions we consider to be relevant:

- (1) Definition and principles of academic activity;
- (2) Academic situation in Romania;
- (3) Convergence dynamics and vehicle;
- (4) Solutions of principle to achieve the convergence of Romania’s academic activity with EU.

3.1. Definition and principles of academic activity

Taking account of the complex semantics of the „convergence” notion we may structure a definition of the approached themes in the paper:

THE CONVERGENCE OF ACADEMIC ACTIVITY represents a confluence, meeting, contact, intersection, intermission, cross, reunion, connection, concentration, respectively the evolution towards a common system of educational development.

The general context shows us that we must have in view the general present specificity of academic activity, respectively that, in the present context, we can’t ignore the **globalization concept** that refers to „*the diminishing of the worlds and the increase of the awareness degree of the world as a whole*” [7]. From the beginning we will have in mind a thing, namely that the „whole” presupposes the idea of *CONVERGENCE*, i.e. towards a unity of the whole argued by levelling tendencies and ones that impose a unique model. That is why we militate for the idea that the convergence process must be **ETHICALLY** regarded, taking into account national identities that regularly are complementary, based on unanimously accepted principles and rules of „unity in diversity”, in conformity with the *Living planet* model and the **bioharmonism paradigm** [4]. In other

words, at continental level should result an **efficient and multipolar academic system, in dynamic balance (permanently adaptable)**.

The **pragmatic aspect** determines that thus **academic convergence** may implicitly lead to the reduction of costs in education through compatibility, to acceleration of changes and communication, to efficiency increase of academic activity at European level, to avoidance of deepening educational differences, to the break-up of certain bankrupt branches, with potential to destabilize economic life and others. The result will be that human resource will have necessary competences to build a real knowledge society at European level (and not only).

3.2. The academic situation in Romania

A short diagnosis shows us that, unfortunately, Romanian school does not look good, in conformity with certain EU data (2017): Romania is the EU country with the less money allocated to education; - The system is adrift by school abandon for the segment 18-24 years old, which is above 18 % (especially in rural space and among Roma and pupils' obliteration from university education); - Unfortunately Romania is on the 3rd place in Europe as for the number of youngsters that do NOT study at a faculty; - Half of the school pupils do not have the minimum level of competences, i.e. potential students are poorly prepared; - Superior study graduates (those of 30-34 years) are averaging 25 % in Romania, face to approximately 40% in EU ; - Adult participation at the continuous educational process is under 2% in Romania, face to approx.11% the average in EU. Another eloquent aspect of *educational disharmony* is the comparison between urban and rural environment, it being extremely concerning in the rural environment (Table 1) [1].

Table 1. Diagnosis regarding the educational level in Romania in function of the geographic zone

Zone	UM	Primary + Gymnasium	High school	Professional	Post-high school + Foremen	Superior	Total
URBAN	no.	491,998	674,662	198,988	101,420	457,664	1,924,732
	%	25.56	35.05	10.34	5.27	23.78	100
RURAL	no.	381,797	44,911	38,021	2,555	330	467,614
	%	81.65	9.60	8.13	0.55	0.07	100

There is observed a really alarming situation (reference the year 2018), i.e. only approx. 19.14 % of the total children and youngsters that study in Romania have graduated superior education.

Therefore during the last decades it is registered a strong *individual de-professionalization, concomitantly with an institutional deprofessionalization*

(!). A reconceptualization of the university didactic and research field becomes imperiously necessary, concomitantly with the convergence at the EU system.

The reduced weight of superior study graduates and their precarious quality risks to create a lack of competences in sectors that need a high degree of knowledge and, finally, to limit Romania's economic progress.

It becomes compulsory TO AVOID individual and institutional de-professionalization taking account of the following aspects of great importance. We can speak about the fact that today to destroy a nation doesn't need atomic bombs nor continental ballistic rockets, but it is enough to reduce education quality and allow fraud at students' exams, situation in which (elements found at different universities from less developed countries): Patients die in the hands of such doctors; Buildings cave in being built by such engineers; Money is lost in the hands of such economists; Justice evaporates in the hands of such jurists and judges.

In such a dramatic situation the conclusion is obvious: **The education crash is the nation crash!** Therefore it becomes more than opportune the **convergence** of academic life from Romania with the one in EU and the finding of **solutions** to achieve this process.

3.3. Convergence dynamics and vehicle

Concretely, academic convergence from Romania with the one from the European Union is expressed by having the same aim, by finding common elements, respectively structural and functional similarities of the educational system with its components in an as good as possible harmonization.

Thus „convergence” offers the finding of solutions to effectively achieve the social mission of transforming university in a center of educational resources and of services offered to the community.

Pragmatically, academic activity found at the level of education is the *process* of systematically influencing (in organized manner too) the formation and development of intellectual, moral, physic etc. characteristics of children, youngsters or men or human collectivities by education.

The importance of school gets above (of different educational institutions) in getting fundamental humanist knowledge and meta-knowledge (Fig.1).

Fig.1. The education process on direction of getting „knowledge” necessary for the formation level geographically compatible in the 21st century

3.4. Solutions of principle for the convergence of the academic activity from Romania with the one in the European Union

More important solutions for the process of academic convergence with EU have potential of **efficiency growth of** academic activity, through a good relation between the obtained results and efforts made for the system financing; development of university study programs centered on the creation of competences (especially practical ones), adapting European similar models; initial formation of professors by teaching master degree; creation of „attractors”, of course in order to attract motivated university teaching staff and to implement research and teaching projects with **linking performance pay at individual level** (on meritocracy principles: welfare and social position are got through performance validated by correct competition, by talent and demonstrated competences).

The principle of teaching staff meritocracy: obligatory scores by the *Teaching file* and *Research file* that will stay at the basis of academic activities (of promotion, of continuing activity after retirement age etc.) and the two pay fractions in

conformity with the legal mission in university academic activity: the teaching one and the research one.

One can reach meritocracy only by education in general, and qualitative teaching in special. Therefore, in modifying attitude and behavior, essential is the **reform of the educational system**. Education along one's whole life (LLL) must be achieved by an ever larger part of the society at superior level and that is why university institutions must pass to a new **teaching paradigm**. In this regard, a convergent direction and of concrete action might have the following characteristics [2,5], in synthesis adapted in Table 2.

Table 2. Elements of reform and harmonization with the 21st century realities for the educational system at University level

Old paradigm	New paradigm
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • « Ivory tower » university 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • « Social partner » university
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Student = 18-25 year old young person 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Student from birth to death
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multicultural approach 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global approach
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Brick and mortar” type formation: learn in order to know and to do 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Bits and bytes” formation type: learn in order to be and to live in community
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assisted, static university 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entrepreneurial university
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unilateral approach: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Centered on institution - Financed by government - Technology, an expense 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multilateral approach: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Centered on market - Financed by market - Technology, an investment
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teaching job for life 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous performance with market value (periodical reaccreditations)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Trouble” student 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • « Client » student
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teaching in amphitheater and classrooms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teaching in any adequate place
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Books, main teaching material 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversified information when requested
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Everything that may be got by individual assimilation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Courses at request, multi-disciplinary, team work
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Calendar of the university year 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • University as an idea, adaptability, real autonomy in official university year
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Graduation diploma 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learning along one's own life, with diplomas „<i>in crescendo</i>”, linked to financial remuneration.

An important step to adopt the new paradigm from Table 2 is certainly represented by the convergence process with the present European model, but which, at its turn, is in transition towards the Knowledge Society.

Indicative MODEL proposal for growth efficiency of the academic process by convergence and compatibility with European universities

There may be kept progressive elements from the present university organization, but to improve the quality of the academic activity there is necessary harmonization of teaching and research elements of the university act and de-bureaucratization of the present system. As a first stage, the **ELIMINATION of present dysfunctions from the Romanian university management** becomes useful, which will allow to implement solutions that induce RO-EU convergence (Table 3).

Table 3. Decalogue of the convergence of the Romanian academic system with the EU one

No.	Element of convergence	Specification
1	Entrepreneurial superior education	- The state or financing foundation consider the allocated sums as an investment in education, in regime of project, respectively on structures of expenses and on activities or on actions, the allocation being made in instalments with justification in order to get the next instalment. For example the circulating fund (wages + utilities) through the basic educational fund, at which, by competitive project, go on: the fund for development; the fund for research; the fund for academic activities, the reserve fund etc.
2	Controlled utilization of financial funds	- Investment in laboratories and equipment for research and educational activity (objective: compatibilization with the European level);
3	Harmonization of the financing flow	- Separate financing on education and research direction concerning the wage level of the university educational staff (objective to encourage the access of projects in university research, similar to the situation in EU);
4	University restructuring	- Reorganization may be done by fusion (in order to become efficient), with forming Schools on fields, but also avoiding superposition in organization (ex. a faculty should obligatorily have at least two departments, because at one department in a faculty there appear superposition between the department council and the faculty one and between the department director and the dean);
5	Optimization of the numeric model	- Students may be assigned in universities with medium capacity, of approx. 30,000 de students. In perspective, everything depends on the country's demographic policy. Hoping to have an ascendant demographic flow, then to widen the bases from 19% with superior education at compatible level with the EU average (which is approx. 35 %), at which there may be added foreign students etc., the situation may forecast large universities in Romania (60-80 thousands of students). In this scenario in Romania there should be organized 15-20 large universities even from now (not irrationally abolished, but fusion and reorganization of the existing ones, with locations in different localities);

Convergence of academic activity between Romania and European Union

6	Department framework	- On department specialty (without supplementary functions and without wage supplements), but important for the organization of academic activity and for communication between full professor (coordinator of the specialty department) and the other education staff from the same specialty (especially with University assistants), as well as with associated staff (technicians, laboratory assistants etc.)
7	Multiple integration in education	- Applying the known idea of integrating education with research and production by rapid technological transfer (to make an exchange of experience between specialists in multinationals, for example, as a rule formed at „mother firms” and university educational staff that know the problem, being in fact trainers from superior education. As a result: the laboratory and course program may rapidly be adapted in conformity with last generation technologies and production demands).
8	Managing positions in universities	- Functions of rector, dean, director of department should be for a period of maximum two mandates of four years; the possibility to candidate for the third mandate only if, from proved objective motives, the second mandate has been interrupted for a period at least as long as 50 % from a mandate (NB – there must urgently be removed from the education law the phrase „complete” mandates).
9	Flexibility and personalization of the analytical program	- In the program 60 % obligatory disciplines (the fundamental ones and the basic ones; these ones are to be found in basic norms of the educational staff) and 40 % from the list of specialty disciplines, the student to be able to choose and make his own route. As a first example (existing in other countries too) a discipline may be presented if there subscribe at least 5 students.
10	Increase of interest by students' presence at day form study	- Obligatory presence at course at least 50 %, and 100% at laboratory / seminar, but concomitantly with making a students' credit system during their studies and finance return after graduation; at reduced frequency, or without frequency, the presence at course may remain facultative, but not at laboratory/seminars.

Conclusions

(1). The academic convergence has as FINALITY to achieve a harmonious unity, so that at continental level may result an efficient and multipolar academic system (networks), in dynamic balance (permanently adaptable), at which Romania may become as convergent as possible, namely to be part of as many structures as possible and with integrated activity.

(2). Convergence leads to the interconnection of the Romanian academic activity with the EU one by COMPATIBILIZATION and ADAPTATION at today's reality of the educational plan, respectively the laboratory program and course information, but also the research projects, in conformity with last generation

technologies and production demands, investment in laboratories and equipment for research and didactic activity and, last but not least, university reorganization, in relation to success models and European recommendations.

(3). The convergence of Romania with EU and, especially, of education, would allow to AVOID individual and institutional de-professionalization and, at the same time, to avoid the crash (because *educational crash means nation's crash!*) taking account of the reduced weight of superior study graduates in Romania and their precarious professional quality in a too large proportion, risking to create a lack of competences in sectors that need a high degree of knowledge and, finally, to limit the economic development of the country.

(4). Convergence in the research field and the participation at international academic life is *de facto* the most stringent, taking account of the disharmonies in the present Romanian research activity (lack of corresponding financing, valuable human resource hemorrhage, reduced attractiveness from financial and professional point of view by lack of last generation endowments, with de rigueur exceptions, but that you „count on fingers”) etc.

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THE STRUCTURE OF INTERNATIONAL EXCHANGES IN AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS INTENDED FOR INDUSTRY AND HOUSEHOLD USE IN ROMANIA

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Abstract. *Determining the production and forage quality of a permanent grassland is essential for establishing the optimal stocking rate in order to preserve the biodiversity and the traditional landscape. The paper presents an assessment of the productivity of steppic grasslands from the two large geographical entities of the ROSCI 0201 North Dobrogean Plateau protected area, respectively Babadag and Casimcea Plateaus. The grasslands from the Babadag Plateau have undergone an accelerated process of degradation in the last 50 years due to the very large share of sheep and goats, almost 90% of the total grazing livestock, that graze all year round except for the days when the soil is covered with a layer of snow. The grasslands from the Casimcea Plateau have generally maintained their productivity for the last 45-50 years as the structure of the vegetal layer has been better preserved, a situation due to the 27% of the total livestock of cattle and horses that were maintained in the stable in the cold season. Currently, the grazing pressure exceeds carrying capacity of these steppic grasslands for 5.5 times in Babadag and 5 times in Casimcea, which is why it is necessary to balance the structure and number of livestock, expand fodder crops in arable land and implement more efficient management measures.*

Keywords: domestic/foreign commerce, trade balance, industrial/household consumption

1. Introduction

Knowing the international exchanges for agri-food products and beverages, represents for Romania a national necessity both at the decision and execution levels. The presentations given in such a paper by comparing the absolute and percentage values mentioned, the actual situation of these exchanges at national level is highlighted. The comments made show the trends of these export / import exchanges of agri-food products and beverages for the period 2012-2017.

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Through the comparative structure of the levels of the value volume of export/import to basic and processed products, it is finally presented through an analysis of the elements that nominate the levels for industrial and domestic consumption [1]. At the same time, the presented balance sheets created the possibility of knowing the future possibilities in carrying out the export / import exchanges of agri-food products and beverages in Romania.

2. Material and methods

This paper interpretively framed the international trade in agri-food products and beverages in Romania, according to some values of the statistical levels of the period 2012-2017. References were made to basic/primary products and processed ones, and for each in the bivalence of destinations for industry and household consumption [2].

The methodology was focused on the use of the indicators of the normative-constructive system, with presentations in absolute and relative values. In the evolution of the years 2012-2017, comparisons were made showing the trends of international trade activities with agri-food products and beverages in Romania.

All these were completed by determining the annual averages and rates and the coefficient of variation. Thus: the annual average was based on the levels of annual values and the number of years; the growth rate was represented by the average annual growth rate; the coefficient of variation whose values were given by the standard deviation and the string for the respective values with the interpretation of intervals with low value (10% low risk), medium value (10-20% moderate risk) and high value (over 20% risk increased) [4].

All these indicators followed the current knowledge of the level and priority of these international exchanges of agri-food products, but also to outline some perspective trends.

3. Results and discussions

International trade in food and beverage trade is also a problem for Romania based on knowledge of the main structural elements. It is necessary to carry out investigations that need to be linked to the levels of annual export and import developments. All these structures result in knowledge of the elements that condition the levels of industrial and household consumption.

3.1. The evolution of Romania's international export of food and beverages

The evolution of Romania's international export of food and beverages represents an essential element from which to start in the analysis. The values in Table 1

highlight in the dynamics of the years of the analyzed period the structural indicators that analyze the basic (primary) and processed products for industrialization and domestic consumption.

Table 1. The evolution of the international export with food and drinks in Romania, by destinations, for the period 2012-2017

Indicator/Year/MU	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	Annual average	Annual rhythm	St. Dev./ Var. coeff.		
	mil. euro	mil. euro	mil. euro	mil. euro	mil. euro	mil. euro	mil. euro	%	mil. euro	%	
Total goods (intended for international trade) of which	Total goods (intended for international trade) of which	49,562	52,466	54,610	57,392	62,644	53,624	6.8	6,125	11.4	
1. Food & Beverages		2,749	3,737	3,809	3,683	4,411	4,661	3,842	11.1	667	17.4
1.1. Basis products (primary) of which:	Value volume	1,661	2,583	2,640	2,430	3,096	3,215	2,604	14.1	554	21.3
	Comparis on level (%)	100	100	100	100	100	100	-	-	-	-
a. for industry	Value volume	1,472	2,337	2,367	2,160	2,852	2,886	14.4	14.4	519	22.1
	% vs. primary prod.	88.62	90.48	89.66	88.89	92.19	89.77	-	-	-	-
b. for domestic consumption	Value volume	189	246	273	270	244	329	11.7	11.7	46	17.7
	% vs. primary prod.	11.38	9.52	10.34	11.11	7.88	10.23	-	-	-	-
1.2. Processed products of which:	Value volume	1,088	1,154	1,169	1,252	1,315	1,446	5.9	5.9	129	10.5
	% vs. processed prod.	100	100	100	100	100	100	-	-	-	-
a. for industry	Value volume	171	215	199	218	181	198	3.0	3.0	18	9.4
	% vs. processed prod.	15.72	18.63	17.02	17.41	13.76	13.69	-	-	-	-
b. for domestic consumption	Value volume	917	939	970	1,034	1,134	1,248	6.4	6.4	128	12.3
	% vs. processed prod.	84.28	81.37	82.98	82.59	86.24	86.31	-	-	-	-

Source: Statistical Yearbook of Romania, INS, 2015, 2018 [3].

The analysis of all the data presented shows the following:

- the evolution on the annual total of the export of framed foods and drinks is represented by an increasing evolution of the annual value levels. Represents an average of 3,842 million euros to which can be added a coefficient of variation of 17.4%, respectively a medium variation and a moderate pace;
- basic/primary products (from these foods and drinks), are represented by a value evolution but with a variational character. Thus, compared to the annual average of 2,604 million euros, the coefficient of variation of 554 million euros is at a percentage level of 21.3% which is a large variation, an increased annual rate. In the delimitation for destination industry and household consumption it is found: for industrial consumption an increased rate (respectively a large variation of

22.1%), but for household consumption the rate is moderate (the level of 17.7% is a medium variation);

- the processed products are presented as a whole and which show evolutionary levels, at which the coefficient of variation which is 129 thousand euros, which represents a percentage of 10.5%, represents a moderate risk and a medium variation. At the same time, the evolutionary level of the products destined for industry is characterized by a coefficient of variation of 9.4% which represents a small variation and a similar (small) risk. Products for household consumption this coefficient of variation is moderate (by the value of 128 million euros and 12.3%).

In this context of exports within the group of food and beverages both as a whole and of industrial and domestic consumption, there are increasing annual levels. At the same time, however, it can be mentioned that these export operations register small and medium variations that render moderate and low risks.

3.2. The evolution of the international import with food and drinks of Romania

The evolution of the international import with food and drinks of Romania both in total and in the structure of the destination for industry and domestic consumption are shown in Table 2 which complete the overall elements of export with these products.

Regarding these destinations of the products mentioned for the dynamics of 2012-2017, the following can be found:

- the import of food and beverages is an increase for the period 2012-2016, to which the year 2017 registers a decrease. Compared to the average of the analyzed period, of 4,670 million euros, the variation is high (20.9%), and the annual rate is 10.4%;
- with reference to the import of basic / primary products, there is an annual increase that takes place both on the basis of those products intended for industry but also for domestic consumption. The high level of variability (between 21.3% and 33.9%) further delimits the indicators of chained growth that show annual rates between 8.6% and 19.5%;
- processed products show an increase in the succession of years, predominantly being the levels of household consumption (88.19% of the average of total processed products). Regarding the coefficient of variation for the total of these products and those intended for industry, there is a classification at a medium variation and household consumption at a large variation. At the same time, the annual rate is negative for products intended for industry (-3.9%) and positive for

total processed products and household consumption (percentage levels being 8.6% and 11.2% respectively).

The results show that Romania's imports for food and beverages are much higher than exports, with high annual levels of variation for primary products. Structurally analyzed, the values of imports of household products have the highest levels of variation (33.9% for commodities and 21.7% for processed products).

Table 2. The evolution of the international import with food and drinks in Romania, by destinations, during 2012-2017

Indicator/Year/MU	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	Mean	Var. coeff.		Annual rhythm	
	mil. euro	mil. euro	mil. euro	mil. euro	mil. euro	mil. euro	mil. euro	mil. euro	%	%	
Total goods (intended for international trade) of which	54,703	55,317	58,522	62,971	67,364	75,604	62,414	8,047	12.9	6.7	
1. Food & Beverages	3,707	3,904	4,048	4,680	5,587	6,093	4,670	976	20.9	10.4	
1.1. Basis products (primary) of which:	Value volume	1,084	1,220	1,294	1,599	2,024	2,132	1,559	437	28.1	14.5
	Comparison level(%)	100	100	100	100	100	100	-	-	-	-
a. for industry	Value volume	549	573	557	654	870	828	672	143	21.3	8.6
	% vs. primary prod.	50.65	46.97	43.04	40.90	42.98	38.84	-	-	-	-
b. for domestic consumption	Value volume	535	647	737	945	1155	1304	887	301	33.9	19.5
	% vs. primary prod.	49.35	53.03	56.96	59.10	57.06	61.16	-	-	-	-
1.2. Processed products of which:	Value volume	2,623	2,684	2,754	3,080	3,563	3,962	3,111	544	17.5	8.6
	% vs. processed prod.	100	100	100	100	100	100	-	-	-	-
a. for industry	Value volume	572	532	426	478	470	468	491	52	10.6	-3.9
	% vs. processed prod.	21.80	19.82	15.47	15.49	13.19	11.81	-	-	-	-
b. for domestic consumption	Value volume	2,052	2,151	2,328	2,603	3,093	3,494	2,620	568	21.7	11.2
	% vs. processed prod.	78.20	80.18	84.53	84.51	86.81	88.19	-	-	-	-

Source: Statistical Yearbook of Romania, INS, 2014, 2018 [3].

3.3. The structure of the main commercial destinations analyzed by the evolution of the balance of international trade in food and beverages

It was analyzed both in total and in the situation of the main commercial destinations (Table 3).

Table 3. The evolution of the balance of international trade in food and beverages in Romania, by destinat

Indicator/Year/MU		2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	Mean	Variation coefficient	
		mil. euro	%							
Total goods (intended for international trade) of which		-9,634	-5,755	-6,056	-8,361	-9,972	-12,960	-8,790	2,697	-30.7
1. Food & Beverages		-958	-167	-239	-997	-1176	-1432	-828	513	-61.9
1.1. Basis products (primary) of which:	Value volume	577	1,363	1,346	831	1,072	1,083	1,045	303	29.0
	Comparison level (%)	100	100	100	100	100	100			
a.- for industry	Value volume	923	1,764	1,810	1,506	1,982	2,058	1,674	415	24.8
	% vs. primary prod.	159.96	129.42	134.47	181.22	184.88	190.02			
b.- domestic consumption	Value volume	-346	-401	-464	-675	-911	-975	-629	269	42.7
	% vs. primary prod.	-59.96	-29.42	-34.47	-81.22	-84.88	-90.02			
1.2. Processed products of which:	Value volume	-1,535	-1,530	-1,585	-1,828	-2,248	-2,516	-1,874	417	22.3
	% vs. processed prod.	100	100	100	100	100	100			
a - for industry	Value volume	-401	-317	-227	-260	-289	-270	-294	60	20.5
	% vs. processed prod.	26.08	20.73	14.32	14.22	12.86				
b- domestic consumption	Value volume	-1,135	-1,212	-1,358	-1,569	-1,959	-2,246	-1,580	440	27.9
	% vs. processed prod.	73.92	79.27	85.68	85.78	87.14				

Source: Statistical Yearbook of Romania, INS, 2014, 2018 [3].

a) For the whole and the structure by destinations of the trade balance based on the evolution of the values shown in table 1.3, the following can be deduced:

- for the whole balance for all years, there are negative values to which is added an accentuated coefficient of variation (rendered by the percentage value of - 61.9% which indicates a large variation);
- the balance for basic/primary products is positive, but with a large variation (of 29%).

At the same time, there is an interpretative difference for the structure of product destinations for which: products for industry balance values are positive and have

a significant share, the variation remaining high (24.8%); in the case of household consumption where it is found that for all years the balance values are negative, for which there is a large variation (42.7%);

In the case of processed products, the values both on total food and beverages, as well as in the structure of industrial and household consumption destinations, the balance has negative values. At the same time, a large variation can be noticed, which in percentage values are registered variations between 20.5% and 27.7%.

Table 4. The structure of the structural balance of food trade by destination, in Romania, for the period 2012-2017

Indicator/AN/UM			Total goods (intended for international trade) of which	1. Food & Beverages	1.1. Basis products (primary) of which:	a.- for industry	b.- domestic consumption	1.2. Processed products of which:	a. - for industry	b- domestic consumption
Export	2012	%	100.0	6.1	3.7	3.3	0.4	2.4	0.4	2.0
	2013	%	100.0	7.5						
	2014	%	100.0	7.3	5.2	4.7	0.5	2.3	0.4	1.9
	2015	%	100.0	6.7						
	2016	%	100.0	7.7	5.0	4.5	0.5	2.2	0.4	1.8
	2017	%	100.0	7.4						
					4.4	4.0	0.5	2.3	0.4	1.9
Import	2012	%	100.0	6.8	5.4	5.0	0.4	2.3	0.3	2.0
	2013	%	100.0	7.1						
	2014	%	100.0	6.9	2.0	1.0	1.0	4.8	1.0	3.8
	2015	%	100.0	7.4						
	2016	%	100.0	8.3	2.2	1.0	1.2	4.9	1.0	3.9
	2017	%	100.0	8.1						
					2.2	1.0	1.3	4.7	0.7	4.0
					2.5	1.0	1.5	4.9	0.8	4.1
Deviations (+/-)	2012	%	0.0	-0.7	3.0	1.3	1.7	5.3	0.7	4.6
	2013	%	0.0	0.5	2.8	1.1	1.7	5.2	0.6	4.6
					1.7	2.3	-0.6	-2.4	-0.7	-1.7
	2014	%	0.0	0.3	3.0	3.7	-0.7	-2.5	-0.5	-2.0
					2.8	3.6	-0.7	-2.5	-0.3	-2.1
	2015	%	0.0	-0.7	1.9	2.9	-1.0	-2.6	-0.4	-2.2
	2016	%	0.0	-0.6	2.4	3.7	-1.3	-3.0	-0.4	-2.6
2017	%	0.0	-0.6	2.3	3.5	-1.2	-2.9	-0.3	-2.6	

Source: Statistical Yearbook of Romania, INS, 2014, 2018 [3].

b) The balance of the structure of trade in food products was further analyzed by destination with reference to exports and imports for Romania. The comparison of

these activities is shown in Table 4, in which the presentation of the values is given as a percentage, showing the following:

- for export this balance for food and beverages has differentiated levels, with reference to the fact that the values for basic/primary products exceed those processed;
- in the case of import, a reverse situation is found, finding that the annual level of processed products exceeds the basic/primary ones;
- the percentage differences of the two parties (export/import) resulted in negative deviations, these being due to the much higher annual levels of imports compared to exports.

In summary, a dynamic analysis of the levels of this balance shows a decrease which, on the whole, is part of a negative maintenance trend (with reference to the predominance of imports of processed products intended for domestic consumption).

Conclusions

The problems presented regarding the contribution with agri-food products and beverages to the international exchanges for Romania during the years 2012-2017 highlight the following analytical aspects:

- (1). The form of existence of the evolution of the annual value levels of the exports that in the dynamics of the years that register a growth rhythm but also an annual variation.
- (2). Imports with food and beverages register an increase, and at the end of the analyzed period there is a decrease, at the same time being registered the highest variational levels. For the situation of basic/primary products, an increase is reported (according to the products destined for industry), the same growth being maintained but with a very accentuated rhythm also for the products destined for domestic consumption.
- (3). From the analysis of the international trade balance for the main commercial destinations the following can be signalled: for the whole and the structure by destinations the value of the balance is negative, to which is added a large coefficient of variation (both for basic/primary products and processed); for export/import destinations differentiated levels can be found due to the fact that for export the values for basic/primary products exceed those processed and for import a reverse situation is found (the value of processed products exceeds basic/primary). In short, the evolutionary trend of some negative levels results from the overall balance of these export/import structures.

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COMPARATIVE STUDY OF STEPPIC GRASSLANDS PRODUCTIVITY AND GRAZING PRESSURE IN BABADAG AND CASIMCEA PLATEAUS

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Abstract. *Determining the production and forage quality of a permanent grassland is essential for establishing the optimal stocking rate in order to preserve the biodiversity and the traditional landscape. The paper presents an assessment of the productivity of steppic grasslands from the two large geographical entities of the ROSCI 0201 North Dobrogean Plateau protected area, respectively Babadag and Casimcea Plateaus. The grasslands from the Babadag Plateau have undergone an accelerated process of degradation in the last 50 years due to the very large share of sheep and goats, almost 90% of the total grazing livestock, that graze all year round except for the days when the soil is covered with a layer of snow. The grasslands from the Casimcea Plateau have generally maintained their productivity for the last 45-50 years as the structure of the vegetal layer has been better preserved, a situation due to the 27% of the total livestock of cattle and horses that were maintained in the stable in the cold season. Currently, the grazing pressure exceeds carrying capacity of these steppic grasslands for 5.5 times in Babadag and 5 times in Casimcea, which is why it is necessary to balance the structure and number of livestock, expand fodder crops in arable land and implement more efficient management measures.*

Keywords: steppic grasslands, feed productivity, carrying capacity, biodiversity conservation

1. Introduction

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The permanent grasslands from ROSCI0201 The North Dobrogean Plateau are mostly included in the natural habitat of community interest 62C0* Ponto-sarmatic steppes.

The vegetation of these steppic grasslands was studied from a phytosociological point of view, resulting in two synthesis papers for the Babadag Plateau [2] respectively for the Casimcei Plateau [4]. In these papers, the steppic grassland vegetation, respectively the permanent grasslands, were mostly included in *Festuco – Brometea* Class, *Festucetalia valesiaca* Order, *Festucion rupicola* and *Pimpinello - Thymion zygoidi* Alliances, that can be assimilated with habitat type 62C0*.

The studies of the steppic grasslands vegetation were carried out within the POIM Project “Integrated Management of the North Dobrogean Plateau (MiPoNoDo)”, MySMIS code 11696. The studies of Babadag and Casimcea grasslands conducted in the summer of 2019 allowed the reevaluation of their productivity, after almost 45 -50 years, based on floristic surveys according to a new method [5].

Having available the data on livestock for 2018, for the 20 villages within the studied area, it was possible to calculate the current stocking rate for grasslands to be compared with the optimal one from the Babadag and Casimcea plateaus.

These studies are a support for the scientific substantiation of the integrated management measures of this site of great scientific, landscape, economic and multicultural importance [7].

2. Material and methods

To evaluate the productivity turnover of the steppic grasslands from the two geographical formations, the Babadag and Casimcea plateaus, we started by analyzing two synthesis papers regarding the grassland phytocoenosis [2,4].

Between June and July 2019, 67 floristic surveys were conducted on the field on 100 sq m plots [1]. The surveys were accompanied by soil samples taken at a depth of 0-10 cm, samples being analyzed according to the methodology proposed by Florea et al. [3].

The floristic surveys were carried out according to the Klapp - Ellenberg method with the direct percentage appreciation of the species' participation in the vegetal layer, which further facilitates our statistical interpretation.

The data regarding areas of permanent grasslands and livestock for 2018 (cattle, sheep, goats and horses) for 20 villages from our research area were obtained from the Tulcea County Agricultural Directorate.

From the total number of villages from our area of interest, 13 of them (Babadag, Ceamurlia de Jos, Cerna, Ciucurova, Dorobanț u, Horia, Izvoarele, Jurilovca, Mihai Bravu, Nalbant, Pecineaga, Sarichioi and Slava Cercheză) are located in Babadag Plateau, the rest of the villages (Baia, Beidaud, Casimcea, Dăeni, Ostrov, Stejaru and Topolog) being located in Casimcei Plateau (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. Research area, with Babadag Plateau at North and Casimcei Plateau at South

The evaluation of the productivity of the grasslands (grazing land value and fodder production) was made according to the new method based on floristic survey [5].

The assessment of the grazing land value and the stocking rate depending on the production, the optimal grazing period and the necessary feed for 1 LU (Livestock Unit), respectively 65 kg of grass per day of grazing, was carried out after Marușca et al. [5].

The evaluation of the productivity of the grasslands based on floristic survey allowed us to capitalize on some older studies of grassland vegetation and compare them with more recent ones in order to assess the evolution in time of floristic and economic parameters.

3. Results and discussions

The results on the main physical and agrochemical characteristics of the soils in the studied areas are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Average physical and agrochemical characteristics of the soils of 62C0* habitat type from the Babadag and Casimcea Plateaus for June – July 2019

Specification	UM	Babadag (B) (26 surveys)			Casimcea (C) (41 surveys)			Differences C - B		
		Min.	Max.	Avg.	Min.	Max.	Avg.	+	-	%
Soil scheleton	%	0.3	39.8	6.18	0	49.9	7.27	+ 1.09		118
pH	ind.	6.29	8.27	7.59	5.33	8.32	6.72	- 0.87		89
Carbonates	%	0	34.1	9.86	0	27.9	2.56	- 7.30		26
Humus	%	1.66	15.87	6.52	2.15	9.78	6.33	- 0.19		97
N	%	0.144	0.708	0.350	0.141	0.540	0.330	- 0.02		94
P _{AL}	mg/kg	4	42	12.15	5	137	16.63	+ 4.48		137
K _{AL}	mg/kg	133	696	263	99	541	223	- 40		88

From these data it is found that the soils in Casimcea, compared to Babadag, have a higher skeleton content (2-25 mm), with a more acidic pH reaction due to the much lower carbonate content.

The explanation is found in the geological substrate composed in Casimcea, especially of "green shales" (green siltite, fine sandstones and quartz-feldspars, hydrothermal quartz, paragnaisse, rhyolite, etc.) and in Babadag from Upper Cretaceous blankets (fine sandstone limestones, microsparitic and silicified, fine calcarenite, etc.), on which basic reaction soils were formed. The total humus and nitrogen content is about the same with a slight increase of 3-6% in Babadag. In contrast, mobile phosphorus is 37% higher and mobile potassium 12% lower in the soils of Casimcea than Babadag.

Generally speaking, the soils in the two locations are weakly acidic to neutral basic, very poor in mobile phosphorus and medium to well-supplied in mobile potassium. On these soils a diversified herbaceous vegetation has developed, used currently mainly by grazing (overgrazing) (Table 2).

The floristic composition of the 67 floristic surveys is made up of 98 more important species, of which 21 species from the Poaceae family, 14 species from the Fabaceae family and 63 species from other botanical families.

Table 2. Comparative situation of the floristic composition and productivity of the 62C0* Ponto - Sarmatic steppes natural habitat from the Babadag and Casimcea Plateaus

SPECIES	Participation %		Differences C - B		Index	
	Babadag	Casimcea	+, -	%	F*	M**
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
POACEAE						
<i>Festuca valesiaca</i>	15.08	27.12	+12.05	180	5	3
<i>Botriochloa ischaemum</i>	21.12	7.93	-13.19	38	3	0
<i>Stipa capillata</i>	4.46	4.59	+0.12	103	3	0
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	1.77	6.54	+4.77	369	6	2
<i>Stipa ucrainica</i>	1.50	0.10	-1.40	7	3	0
<i>Poa bulbosa</i>	1.27	1.78	+0.51	140	6	1
<i>Festuca callieri</i>	0.77	0.29	-0.48	38	5	2
<i>Koeleria splendens</i>	0.69	0.24	-0.45	35	5	3
<i>Bromus tectorum</i>	0.65	0.54	-0.12	82	5	2
<i>Agropyron cristatus</i>	0.58	1.02	+0.45	178	7	5
<i>Poa angustifolia</i>	0.46	0.00	-0.46	0	7	5
<i>Stipa tirsia</i>	0.46	0.00	-0.46	0	3	0
<i>Bromus hordeacens</i>	0.12	0.32	+0.20	275	3	0
<i>Chrysopogon gryllus</i>	0.38	0.90	+0.52	235	4	7
<i>Hordeum murinum</i>	0.15	0.00	-0.15	0	5	3
<i>Bromus inermis</i>	0.04	0.00	-0.04	0	8	8
<i>Koeleria braevis</i>	0.00	0.85	+0.85	0	5	3
<i>Bromus riparius</i>	0.00	0.07	+0.07	0	3	0
<i>Dactylis glomerata</i>	0.00	0.02	+0.02	0	9	8
<i>Lolium perenne</i>	0.00	0.02	+0.02	0	9	8
<i>Phleum phleoides</i>	0.00	0.02	+0.02	0	6	4
FABACEAE						
<i>Medicago falcata</i>	0.62	0.05	-0.57	8	7	6
<i>Astragalus onobrychis</i>	0.38	0.02	-0.36	6	5	4
<i>Medicago lupulina</i>	0.19	0.12	-0.07	63	8	3
<i>Onobrychis viciifolia</i>	0.12	0.10	-0.02	85	8	8
<i>Astragalus glaucus</i>	0.08	0.20	+0.12	254	5	4
<i>Coronilla varia</i>	0.08	0.00	-0.08	0	1	0
<i>Trifolium arvense</i>	0.08	0.00	-0.08	0	4	2
<i>Trifolium campestre</i>	0.08	0.00	-0.08	0	7	2
<i>Vicia cracca</i>	0.04	0.00	-0.04	0	7	6
<i>Vicia vilosa</i>	0.04	0.00	-0.04	0	7	6
<i>Lathyrus pratensis</i>	0.04	0.00	-0.04	0	7	6
<i>Coronilla scorpioides</i>	0.04	0.00	-0.04	0	3	0
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	0.00	0.20	+0.20	0	6	2
<i>Medicago minima</i>	0.00	0.07	+0.07	0	7	1
OTHER FAMILIES						
<i>Artemisia austriaca</i>	2.81	4.78	+1.97	170	2	0
<i>Thymus pannonicus</i>	3.81	4.49	+0.68	118	4	2
<i>Teucrium chamaedrys</i>	3.19	0.76	-2.44	24	3	0

<i>Euphorbia sequeriana</i>	2.15	1.73	-0.42	80	1	0
<i>Marrubium peregrinum</i>	1.69	0.15	-1.55	9	3	0
<i>Convolvulus cantabricus</i>	1.69	0.07	-1.62	4	3	0
<i>Achillea pannonica</i>	1.65	0.95	-0.70	58	6	5
<i>Teucrium polium</i>	1.38	0.63	-0.75	46	3	0
<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	1.23	2.07	+0.84	168	3	0
<i>Thymus zygoides</i>	1.23	1.12	-0.11	91	4	1
<i>Eryngium campestre</i>	1.19	1.83	+0.64	153	3	0
<i>Sanguisorba minor</i>	1.12	0.41	-0.70	37	6	3
<i>Potentilla argentea</i>	1.04	0.95	-0.09	92	4	2
<i>Fragaria viridis</i>	0.77	0.10	-0.67	13	4	1
<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	0.65	0.59	-0.07	90	6	1
<i>Achillea coarctata</i>	0.62	0.78	+0.17	127	6	3
<i>Adonis vernalis</i>	0.62	0.00	-0.62	0	1	0
<i>Inula ochulus-christi</i>	0.58	0.07	-0.50	13	3	0
<i>Euphorbia glareosa</i>	0.46	0.02	-0.44	5	1	0
<i>Dianthus nardiformis</i>	0.42	0.73	+0.31	173	3	0
<i>Daucus carota</i>	0.38	0.00	-0.38	0	6	5
<i>Potentilla recta</i>	0.35	0.10	-0.25	28	5	2
<i>Galium humifusum</i>	0.31	0.37	+0.06	119	5	2
<i>Sedum hildebrandti</i>	0.27	0.93	+0.66	344	3	0
<i>Carpinus orientalis</i>	0.23	0.00	-0.23	0	3	0
<i>Asperula cynanchica</i>	0.19	0.15	-0.05	76	3	0
<i>Pimpinella tragioides</i>	0.19	0.12	-0.07	63	3	0
<i>Taraxacum serotinum</i>	0.19	0.05	-0.14	25	5	2
<i>Agrimonia eupatoria</i>	0.19	0.02	-0.17	13	3	0
<i>Ajuga chamaepitys</i>	0.19	0.02	-0.17	13	3	0
<i>Cruciata pedemontana</i>	0.15	0.24	+0.09	159	3	0
<i>Potentilla pedata</i>	0.15	0.02	-0.13	16	4	2
<i>Euphorbia nicaeensis</i>	0.12	0.49	+0.37	423	1	0
<i>Cichorium intybus</i>	0.12	0.22	+0.10	190	5	6
<i>Salvia nutans</i>	0.12	0.02	-0.09	21	4	2
<i>Convolvulus arvensis</i>	0.08	0.10	+0.02	127	7	6
<i>Xeranthemum annuum</i>	0.08	0.10	+0.02	127	3	0
<i>Echinops ruthenicus</i>	0.08	0.05	-0.03	63	3	0
<i>Reseda lutea</i>	0.08	0.02	-0.05	32	3	0
<i>Haplophyllum suaveolens</i>	0.08	0.00	-0.08	0	3	0
<i>Chondrilla juncea</i>	0.04	0.27	+0.23	698	3	0
<i>Alyssum alyssoides</i>	0.04	0.10	+0.06	254	3	0
<i>Berteroa incana</i>	0.04	0.10	+0.06	254	3	0
<i>Adonis flammea</i>	0.04	0.02	-0.01	63	3	0
<i>Valerianella lacusta</i>	0.04	0.02	-0.01	63	3	0
<i>Alyssum hirsutum</i>	0.04	0.00	-0.04	0	3	0
<i>Ajuga laxmanii</i>	0.04	0.00	-0.04	0	4	2
<i>Herniaria glabra</i>	0.00	0.54	+0.54	0	3	0
<i>Centaurea diffusa</i>	0.00	0.37	+0.37	0	4	4
<i>Rosa pimpinellifolia</i>	0.00	0.29	+0.29	0	3	0

<i>Hieracium pilosella</i>	0.00	0.17	+0.17	0	4	1
<i>Scleranthus perennis</i>	0.00	0.12	+0.12	0	3	0
<i>Erodium cicutarium</i>	0.00	0.10	+0.10	0	3	0
<i>Achillea setacea</i>	0.00	0.07	+0.07	0	6	3
<i>Carduus nutans</i>	0.00	0.07	+0.07	0	3	0
<i>Herniaria hirsuta</i>	0.00	0.05	+0.05	0	3	0
<i>Anthemis ruthenica</i>	0.00	0.05	+0.05	0	3	0
<i>Hieracium bauhinii</i>	0.00	0.05	+0.05	0	4	1
<i>Echium vulgare</i>	0.00	0.05	+0.05	0	4	3
<i>Galium verum</i>	0.00	0.05	+0.05	0	5	4
<i>Linum austriacum</i>	0.00	0.02	+0.02	0	3	0
<i>Sanguisorba officinalis</i>	0.00	0.02	+0.02	0	7	5
<i>Scleranthus annuus</i>	0.00	0.02	+0.02	0	3	0
Gaps in vegetation	16.61	19.05	+2.44	115	X	X
Total non-forage species (F1-3)	47.27	29.83	-17.44	63	X	X
Total forage species (F4-9)	36.12	51.12	+15.00	142	X	X
Grazing (Pastoral) Value (PV)	20.59	29.13	+8.54	141	X	X
Feed quality assessment	Week	Mediocre	X	X	X	X
Average phytomass index (M)	1.03	1.42	X	X	X	X
Useful grass production (GM t/ha)	2.06	2.84	+0.78	138	X	X
Stocking rate (LU/ha)	0.17	0.24	+0.70	141	X	X
Stocking rate evaluation	Degraded	Very week	X	X	X	X

*) F = Feed value index

**) M = Useful green mass index

In Casimcea there are over 19% gaps in vegetation, 30% participation of non-forage species and over 51% forage species. In Babadag we have almost 17% gaps, over 47% participation in the vegetal layer with non-forage species and only 36% forage species that can be consumed by livestock.

As a result of this structure, from the interpretation of data resulted that the grazing (pastoral) value in Casimcea is 41% higher than in Babadag, the production of useful phytomass (fodder) higher by 38% and obviously the optimal stocking rate is 41% higher.

It can be seen that the grazing value of 21-29 is weak to mediocre, the production of green fodder mass is 2.1 - 2.8 t/ha which allows an optimal stocking rate of 0.17 - 0.24 LU/ha, indicating degraded to very weak grasslands.

One of the main causes of the very low level of productivity of steppic grasslands in addition to the local environmental conditions with drier climate and lack of water in the soil is overgrazing and the absence of the most basic maintenance works (cleaning of grasslands, fertilization, etc.).

In order to evaluate the “grazing (pastoral) pressure” we used the data regarding the surface of the grasslands and livestock for the 20 villages from our area of interest, establishing the current stocking rate (LU/hectare) (Table 3).

Table 3. Surface of permanent grasslands, livestock and stocking rate in the Babadag and Casimcea Plateaus

Specification	UM	Babadag	Casimcea	Differences C - B	
				+, -	%
Permanant grasslands	ha	15,410	14,020	-1,390	91
Grazing livestock(individuals):					
Cattle	no.	1,767	4,968	+ 3,201	281
Sheep	no.	66,943	65,893	- 1,050	98
Goats	no.	25,556	21,495	- 4,601	84
Horses	no.	241	1,081	+ 840	448
Livestock Unit (nr. LU)					
Cattle (x 0,75)	no.	1,325	3,726	+ 2,401	281
Sheep (x 0,14)	no.	9,372	9,225	- 1,470	98
Goats(x 0,14)	no.	3,578	3,004	- 574	84
Horses (x 0,80)	no.	193	865	+ 672	448
Total Livestock (LU)	no.	14,468	16,815	+ 2,347	116
Livestock structure (% LU)					
Cattle	%	9.2	22.2	+ 13.0	241
Sheep	%	64.8	54.9	- 9.9	85
Goats	%	24.7	17.8	- 6.9	72
Horses	%	1.3	5.1	+ 3.8	392
Stocking Rate	LU/ha	0.94	1.20	+ 0.26	128

From these data it results that from the total area of grasslands of 29,430 hectares in 2018, approx. 52% belonged to Babadag and 48% to Casimcea Plateau. If the areas of grasslands are substantially equal, the livestock as species are quite differentiated.

Thus, in Casimcea there are over 3,000 LU more cattle and horses and over 2,000 fewer sheep and goats out of the almost 17,000 LU respectively 2,300 LU higher than Babadag which has 14,500 LU in total.

This structure in favor of cattle and horses that better respect the grazing and housing season in Casimcea compared to the more numerous sheep and goats that graze all year round in Babadag, is one of the important factors of more severe degradation of productivity of grasslands in Babadag, compared to Casimcea.

The stocking rate for 2018 was 28% higher in Casimcea (1.2 LU/ha) compared to Babadag (0.94 LU/ha).

The long-term evolution of the productivity of assessed grasslands has also benefited the grasslands in the Casimcei Plateau, although the soil conditions seem to be more favorable in the Babadag Plateau (Table 4).

Table 4. Evolution of grasslands productivity and stocking rate from the Babadag and Casimcea Plateaus

Specification	UM	Babadag Plateau				Casimcei Plateau			
		1970	2019	Dif.+, -	%	1975	2019	Dif.+, -	%
Grazing (pastoral) Value (PV)	ind.	31.9	20.6	-11.3	65	19.2	29.1	+9.9	151
Feed production	t/ha	4.47	2.06	-2.41	46	2.62	2.84	+0.22	108
Optimal stocking rate	LU /ha	0.37	0.17	-0.20	46	0.22	0.24	+0.02	108
Current stocking rate	LU /ha	x	0.94	x	x	x	1.20	x	x
Current difference from optimal	+, -	x	+0.77	x	x	x	+0.96	x	x
	%	x	553	x	x	x	500	x	x

It is observed that the pastoral value in Babadag decreases by 11 and the fodder production decreases by 2.4 t/ha GM (Green Mass) in the period 1970-2019 and in Casimcea it increases by 10, the fodder production being almost constant in the period 1975-2019.

Comparing the current stocking rate with the optimal one resulting from the calculation, it is found that the stocking rate is 5.5 times higher in the Babadag Plateau and 5 times higher in the Casimcei Plateau, compared to the carrying capacity of these steppic grasslands.

Similar analyzes performed according to the same methodology in the Măcinului Mountains, located north of the Babadag plateau, showed a stocking rate approximately 2 times higher than the current carrying capacity [6].

These results raise a serious alarm about the need to reduce pastoral pressure on grasslands, by reducing livestock or providing fodder for the current livestock by expanding perennial and annual fodder crops in arable land.

Conclusions

(1). The permanent grasslands of the Order *Festucetalia valesiacae* with the Alliances *Festucion rupicolae* and *Pimpinello – Thymion zygioidi* which is assimilated with Habitat 62C0* Ponto-sarmatic steppes from the Babadag and Casimcea Plateaus are currently in a very advanced stage of degradation, floristic and economic.

- (2). The main cause of the degradation of the pastoral value and the production of useful phytomass is the overgrazing which is 5.5 times in Babadag and 5 times in Casimcea, over the current carrying capacity.
- (3). The grasslands from the Babadag Plateau, with 89.5% sheep and goat from total livestock structure, have degraded at a faster rate in the last 45-50 years, compared to Casimcea with 72.7% sheep and goats in the total LU, where productivity and biodiversity have suffered less.
- (4). Reducing the pastoral pressure to the estimated level of 0.17 LU/ha in Babadag and 0.22 LU/ha in Casimcea and cultivating annual and perennial forage plants in arable lands to ensure the necessary feed for existing livestock in the 20 territorial administrative units (villages), is the most viable solution for the future.
- (5). Balancing the structure between sheep, goats and cattle and a minimum of management measures on these grasslands, would contribute to the conservation of biodiversity and protection of the environment and landscapes.

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